

ENHANCING LANGUAGE LEARNER'S GRAMMAR SKILLS USING ICT TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *The issues of enhancing language learner's grammar skills using ict technologies in the process of globalization along with technological progress are considered today, they are far from being the latest phenomena, but their development does not stand still. ICTs, including television, radio, and new digital technologies such as the Internet and computers, are powerful tools for changing the nature of education. ICTs not only help expand access to education, but also strengthen the relevance of education and improve its quality.*

Keywords: *information, communication, engineer, English language, grammar, model, process, technology, education, learning.*

The process of globalization together with technological progress today is far from being the latest phenomena, but their development does not stand still. ICTs, including television, radio, and new digital technologies such as the Internet and computers, are powerful tools for changing the nature of education. ICTs not only help expand access to education, but also strengthen the relevance of education and improve its quality.

ICT tools as software, software hardware and technical means that operate on the basis of microprocessor and computer technology. ICTs are modern means of information broadcasting and exchange that carry out operations for collecting, accumulating, storing, processing and transmitting information and providing the opportunity to access information resources of local and global computer networks [Robert 2007: 15].

ICTs are actively used in modern systems of open and distance education to transmit information and ensure interaction between teacher and student. But, of course, the process of informatization affected not only higher educational institutions and various courses that provide educational services remotely, but also schools. The educational standard of the new generation obliges the modern primary education teacher not only to have knowledge in the field of ICT, but also to be a specialist in its application in his professional activities, in other words, to have ICT competence. One of the main goals of teaching a foreign language is the formation of foreign language communicative competence in all the diversity of its components (linguistic, speech, sociocultural, compensatory, educational and cognitive), necessary for communication in the social, every day and professional spheres.

The history of methods of teaching foreign languages proves that the attitude towards grammar has never been unambiguous; it determined the specifics of the approach, method and technique of teaching. At the same time, the role assigned to grammatical theory was either exaggerated, for example, during the times of the grammar-translation method, or underestimated or completely excluded, for example, in direct methods. In classical Greek, grammar included the following three components: - Syntax - the rules by which words are combined into larger structures such as phrases and clauses, and the relationships between them.

For example, in the English language there is a category of completeness of action, which is absent in the Uzbek language. Such differences in languages cause difficulties in learning a

foreign language [10-14]. Professor Penny Ur notes that grammar not only influences the correct combination of grammatical units, but also influences the meaning conveyed by them. Unfortunately, teaching grammatical meanings is often neglected in textbooks for schoolchildren; the authors give preference to teaching the construction of word forms. It is important to understand that knowing how this or that verb tense is constructed without knowing what exactly this construction means and how it differs from others is useless. It is the meanings of structures that cause the greatest difficulty for students [Ur 1996: 16]. Like linguists, methodologists argue about the inherent importance of teaching grammar as an aspect of language. Of course, not all languages have identical structures. So, for example, in the English language there is a category of completeness of action, which is absent in the Uzbek language. Such differences in languages cause difficulties in learning a foreign language .

Therefore, the use of ICT in teaching a foreign language will be aimed at developing speech skills (listening, reading, speaking, writing), language skills (grammatical, lexical, phonetic) and the formation of sociocultural and intercultural competencies, and ICT competence of a foreign language teacher will consist in the ability apply the entire arsenal of ICT in the process of teaching aspects of a foreign language and types of speech activity [5]. To study the problem we are considering, we need to distinguish between two important terms: “competence” and “competence”. In this work, following A.V. Khutorsky, we understand competence as “a set of interrelated personality qualities (motivation, knowledge, abilities, skills, methods of activity) specified in relation to a certain range of objects and processes necessary for high-quality and productive activity in relation to them”. Competence is “possession, possession by a person of the appropriate competence, including his personal attitude towards it and the subject of activity” [18]. In other words, competence is the level of formation of competence as a theoretical construct. Based on the above, under the ICT competence of a foreign language teacher, we consider “a construct consisting of theoretical knowledge about modern information and communication technologies and practical skills to create and use educational Internet resources, Web 2.0 social services and other ICTs in the process of developing language skills and development of students’ speech skills when teaching a foreign language and the culture of the country of the language being studied” [17].

ICT competence of a foreign language teacher in structural terms includes the following five interrelated components: value-motivational, cognitive, operational, communicative and reflective. The values and motivational component presupposes awareness of the need to use ICT in teaching, taking initiative in the use of ICT and the desire for self-improvement in the use of new ICT. The cognitive component is characterized by the presence of certain knowledge about the range of modern ICTs, which can be applied in teaching a foreign language and the culture of the country of the language being studied. The operational component is determined by the implementation of knowledge in practice.

The communicative component includes the teacher’s ability to share accumulated knowledge and skills, as well as discuss with colleagues the experience of using ICT in teaching a foreign language. The reflexive component lies in the teacher’s ability to carry out self-assessment and introspection of his activities in the use of ICT in the teaching and educational process with the aim of constantly improving innovative methods [3]. The development of ICT competence in a foreign language teacher allows the following: □ transfer of Internet technologies widely used by students from their lives into the educational process, which helps to increase

students' motivation to learn a foreign language; □ introducing the studied material into extracurricular activities, which is relevant when reducing hours for studying a foreign language; - implementation in practice of such pedagogical technology as "learning in cooperation"; - improving students' ability to conduct independent learning activities through ICT, which is necessary for self-education throughout life; - individualization and differentiation of educational activities. In my opinion, the introduction of ICT takes into account the age characteristics of primary school students. The use of gaming and didactic capabilities of the computer makes the learning process smoother. Most of the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in lessons are not used by students in extracurricular activities, so their practical value is lost and their strength is reduced. The application of knowledge, skills and abilities in a gaming computer environment leads to their actualization and motivation for their acquisition.

The use of computer technology also makes it possible to partially relieve high emotional tension, diversify and enliven the educational process. The main task of a multimedia textbook is to automate all the main stages of learning - from presenting educational material to monitoring knowledge and assessing. At the same time, the obligatory boring educational material is transformed into an exciting, bright, multimedia form with a reasonable share of a gaming approach with extensive use of animation, graphics, sound effects and video clips [11]. The contribution of a foreign language as a school subject to the formation of ICT competence of students includes: preparation of a plan and abstract of a message (including hypermedia); giving a message; creating small text on a computer; recording one's own oral speech in a foreign language in digital form for self-correction; oral presentation accompanied by audio and video support; perception and understanding of basic information in small oral and written messages, including those received by computer means of communication; the use of a computer dictionary, screen translation of individual words" [23].

This "traditional grammar" was presented in textbooks containing exercises for parsing sentences: identifying parts of speech and analyzing sentences. Grammar should be taught out of context, through simulated communication situations. Evaluating the learning process and results requires special attention. Grammar is the aspect of speech that should be taught, not tested. The best way to check the acquisition of grammatical rules is to pay attention to how they are applied in speech [7]. Methods and techniques in teaching grammar are different. Some methodologists advocate traditional teaching of grammar: memorizing the rules and practicing them in practice. However, others argue that learning grammar can have a detrimental effect on motivation to learn a language in general. Both approaches to the grammatical side of speech have their practical justification. Research that dates back to the early 1960s and may seem inconclusive today has shown that teaching grammar does not improve students' writing. Thus, Harris R.D. compared two groups of students: one group was taught grammar through exercises from a standard textbook, while the other group was not taught grammar at all. He found that the grammar group had higher scores on a grammar test, but that the grammar skill was not reflected in their writing. So he proved that the correctness and accuracy of written speech is more likely to be achieved by increasing writing practice. Thus, he concluded that English grammar has little or even a detrimental effect on students' writing accuracy [19-24].

Thus, he proved that this study is not an argument in favor of completely abandoning grammar teaching. On the contrary, consideration of the text as a whole and the structure of its sentences will have a more positive impact on the formation of language competence. Certainly,

approaches that involve writing interventions, where children verbalize sentences before writing, promote effective written language. Teaching grammatical terms helps children discuss the language system and justify the choice of one or another grammatical structure when writing [8]. More recent studies by Andrews R., Torgenson K., Beverton S., et al., confirm the conclusions made earlier. Based on the analysis of 4,691 papers, two main conclusions were drawn: - The teaching of theoretical grammar itself was ineffective. Students taught theoretical grammar found the lessons boring and monotonous. The impact on students' writing proficiency was minimal. - Teaching sentence construction is one of the most effective methods of teaching grammar [9]. Sentence construction is a series of practical techniques for forming a complex sentence from several simple ones. F. O'Hara's study showed that the experimental group trained in sentence construction showed better results than the control group. Teaching sentence construction differs from traditional teaching of theoretical grammar in practicality, and is not associated with teaching a set of rules [O'Hara 1973: 3]. Thus, grammar, being an integral aspect of language, should be taught in teaching the written and spoken form of a language. Since without it it is impossible to fully master language competence. However, a competent teacher needs to take into account the characteristics of students: their age characteristics, level of language readiness, the material taught to them; maintain a balance between the principle of communicativeness and high-quality development of grammatical phenomena. Research shows that teaching grammar is necessary, but the problem of choosing an approach and method of teaching still remains relevant. Thus, some methodologists believe that finding grammatical structures in context and introducing language games using grammatical terminology has a positive effect on students' written speech. And, conversely, exercises out of context, aimed, for example, at identifying parts of speech, are not the most effective type of activity, since this skill is not reflected in written language literacy, and also demotivates students to further study the language [Myhill 2012: 3].

The most practical application traditionally receives a combination of approaches and methods depending on the age of the students, their level of language, the material being studied, in other words, a differentiated approach [6]. So, according to E. N. Solovova, the most effective combination at the initial and middle stages of training will be a combination of inductive and communicative methods. The justification for the need to use the inductive method can be that it is at these stages that the mechanism of linguistic conjecture is formed, and the grammatical phenomena being studied are simple enough to be deduced from the context. At the stage of practicing a grammatical phenomenon, it would be advisable to increase the number of exercises with a communicative-oriented context: grammatical games, acting out communication situations. It is difficult to imagine the formation of a skill from previously independently derived knowledge without the inclusion of a communicative teaching method.

At the senior stages of education, as a rule, the deductive teaching method is used. This is explained by the following factors: a high level of language literacy and academic skills, which allows high school students to independently find the necessary information in reference literature; the complexity of the grammatical structures being studied, which prevents them from being taken out of context without the help of a teacher; developmental tasks of a given age, which presuppose the autonomy of the student, his ability to independently solve problems, self-correction and self-esteem [5]. Thus, the choice of approach and teaching method depends on each specific lesson. The teacher's task is to competently analyze the needs of the student group, the characteristics of the material being taught, and choose the most appropriate way to conduct the lesson.

Traditionally, two approaches have developed in teaching grammar - implicit and explicit. In the first case, teachers give preference to the practical part of training, while in the second, special attention is paid to explaining the rules. The combination of these approaches is a differentiated approach. Let us consider in more detail each of the above approaches. An example of an implicit approach is the structural method, which is a mechanical development of structural models. On the one hand, students develop a “dynamic stereotype”, in other words, a grammatical skill, which means they will be able to automatically use a mechanically developed grammatical structure in their own speech and recognize it in the speech of their interlocutor. On the other hand, such monotonous repetition of form does not contribute to the creative development of students, since the content and verbal value of the sentences is low. As a result, this method can reduce students’ motivation to further study the language.

The formation of ICT competence should take place not only in classes in individual academic subjects, where subject ICT competence is formed, but also within the framework of a supra-subject program for the formation of the development of personal actions, a critical attitude to information and selectivity of its perception, respect for information about private life is being developed other people, the foundations of legal culture in the field of information use. When mastering regulatory ICT, the following is provided: □ assessment of the conditions, algorithms and results of actions performed in the information environment; □ use of action results posted in the information environment to evaluate and correct the action performed; - creation of a digital portfolio of student’s educational achievements. When mastering cognitive ICTs play a key role in such general educational universal activities as: - searching for information; - recording (recording) information using various technical means; □ structuring information, its organization and presentation in the form of diagrams, maps, timelines, etc.; - creation of simple hypermedia messages; □ construction of the simplest models of objects and processes. ICT is an important tool for the formation of communication technologies used: - exchange of hypermedia messages; - performance with audiovisual support; - recording the progress of collective/personal communication; - communication in the digital environment (e-mail, chat, video conference, forum, blog). “The formation of ICT competence of students occurs within the framework of a systemic activity approach.

Mastering the ability to work with information and use ICT tools can also be included in the content of elective courses, clubs, and extracurricular activities for schoolchildren.” As we mentioned above, the goal of training at the initial stage is, first of all, the formation of elementary communicative competence in the main types of speech activity. And it is impossible to achieve this goal without developing fundamental skills in students, in particular grammatical ones. The grammatical side of a language represents syntactic patterns of organization of texts and words, syntagmas and sentences, word formation and form formation. Providing the formation of oral and written communication skills, grammar is of paramount practical importance in teaching any foreign language.

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